
BALANCE CONTROL AND STABILITY OF A TWO-WHEELED ROBOT UTILIZING ADAPTIVE LQR CONTROLLER BASED ON EVOLUTIONARY ALGORITHMS

✉ **Amirreza. Gheitanchian**

Department of Mechatronics Engineering
University of Tabriz
Tabriz, Iran

amirgheitanchian1401@ms.tabrizu.ac.ir

✉ **Seyed Mohammadreza Akrami**

Department of Mechatronics Engineering
University of Tabriz
Tabriz, Iran

mr.akrami@tabrizu.ac.ir

✉ **Amir.A. Ghavifekr**

Department of Electrical Engineering
University of Tabriz
Tabriz, Iran

aa.ghavifekr@tabrizu.ac.ir

✉ **Mohammad Hadi Daman**

Department of Mechatronics Engineering
University of Tabriz
Tabriz, Iran

mh.daman1402@ms.tabrizu.ac.ir

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an intelligent control approach for stabilizing a two-wheeled self-balancing robot (TWSBR) by integrating a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) with the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) algorithm. The nonlinear dynamic model of the robot is first derived using the Lagrangian formulation and linearized around the upright equilibrium point. A conventional LQR controller is designed to provide baseline stabilization; however, its performance strongly depends on the manual selection of weighting matrices, which may not guarantee optimal behavior under all conditions. To overcome this limitation, the GWO algorithm is employed to adaptively tune the LQR feedback gains, minimizing a composite cost function that incorporates state deviations, control effort, and overshoot penalties. Simulations are conducted to compare the classical and GWO-optimized LQR controllers in terms of transient response, steady-state accuracy, and robustness. The results demonstrate that the proposed GWO-LQR controller achieves significantly reduced overshoot, smoother control actions, and enhanced stability compared to the conventional LQR scheme.

Keywords Two-wheeled robot · intelligent controller · robot balance · simulation · system stability

1 Introduction

Two-wheeled self-balancing robots (TWSBRs) represent a class of underactuated, nonlinear, and inherently unstable systems that have drawn significant attention from researchers in control engineering and robotics (1; 2). Due to their unstable dynamics and coupling between translational and rotational motions, precise control design is essential to maintain balance and ensure smooth motion. These robots serve as ideal platforms for investigating control strategies applicable to advanced applications such as personal mobility vehicles, autonomous delivery robots, and rehabilitation devices. Notably, recent advancements in two-wheeled jumping and balancing robots, such as the Ascento robot developed by Klemm, Siegart, and their colleagues, have demonstrated the effectiveness of LQR-assisted whole-body control for highly agile maneuvers on flat terrain and obstacle negotiation (3; 4). Furthermore, maintaining stable balance is a fundamental prerequisite for deploying these robots in human-centric environments, where advanced perception and socially-aware navigation algorithms, such as those pioneered by Alahi *et al.* (5), are required to safely predict human trajectories and avoid collisions in crowded spaces.

Conventional control methods such as Proportional–Integral–Derivative (PID) (6) and Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) have been widely used for stabilizing TWSBRs (7; 8). The LQR controller, in particular, provides an optimal state-feedback law that minimizes a quadratic cost function combining state deviation and control effort. However, the performance of LQR strongly depends on the selection of its weighting matrices Q and R . Determining appropriate values for these matrices is non-trivial, often relying on heuristic or trial-and-error approaches that may yield suboptimal or non-robust performance under varying conditions (9).

One of the most common methods for balancing and stabilizing two-wheeled robots is the combined use of a PID controller and a complementary filter. In this method, the robot’s tilt angle is estimated using data from gyroscope and accelerometer sensors. The complementary filter fuses short-term and long-term sensor information to reduce measurement noise and improve estimation accuracy. The PID controller is then used to actively regulate the tilt angle and maintain the robot’s balance. This approach is advantageous due to its simplicity and low cost; however, it may face limitations in highly dynamic or complex environments (10). Another advanced approach for balancing control in two-wheeled robots is the use of nonlinear adaptive control and the State-Dependent Riccati Equation (SDRE) method. These methods enable the robot to effectively respond to continuous environmental changes and the intrinsic nonlinearities of the system. In the SDRE approach, by solving a Riccati equation that depends on the system’s current state, an optimal controller for nonlinear systems is designed. This allows the controller to utilize the full nonlinear model of the system in its design, leading to excellent performance under complex and varying conditions. However, high computational complexity and the need for an accurate system model are among the main challenges of this approach (11).

To overcome these limitations, metaheuristic optimization algorithms have emerged as powerful tools for automatic tuning of control parameters. Techniques such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) have been successfully applied to optimize controller gains (12; 13; 14). For instance, Fang (14) utilized the particle swarm algorithm to optimize the parameter matrix of an LQR controller to reduce overshoot and oscillation frequency in two-wheeled robots. Nevertheless, these algorithms often suffer from premature convergence or high computational cost. The Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO), inspired by the social hierarchy and hunting behavior of grey wolves, has shown remarkable performance in global optimization tasks due to its balanced exploration and exploitation capabilities, fast convergence rate, and simple implementation (15; 16). Combining these techniques with other methods such as LQR can further enhance system performance in nonlinear and dynamic environments. However, these approaches require careful parameter tuning and a certain level of prior knowledge. For example, SMC requires appropriate design of the sliding surface, and neural networks need sufficient training data. The choice of control method depends on system complexity, disturbance types, and hardware limitations (17). Recently, reinforcement learning (RL) methods have also been applied to control two-wheeled robots. These methods continuously learn and optimize control strategies from experience and collected data, allowing autonomous adaptation to dynamic environments. Although RL techniques have shown promising results in complex and uncertain settings, they generally require considerable computation time and extensive training to converge (18).

This paper proposes an LQR controller optimized using the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) to enhance the stability and dynamic response of a TWSBR. The robot’s dynamic model is derived using the Lagrangian formulation and linearized around the upright equilibrium point. The GWO algorithm is employed to automatically adjust the Q and R matrices of the LQR by minimizing a multi-objective cost function that reflects overshoot, settling time, and control energy. The complete source code and simulation files utilized in this study are publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/HadiDMN/TWSBR-LQR-GWO>.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the system modeling and state-space representation of the TWSBR. Also, it describes the LQR control design and its limitations. Section 3 introduces the GWO-based optimization approach. Section 4 discusses simulation results and analysis. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper with key findings and directions for future research.

2 System Modeling and Controller Design

The two-wheeled self-balancing robot (TWSBR) is an underactuated electromechanical system that maintains an upright position by continuously adjusting the wheel torques. The robot consists of two independently driven wheels attached to a rigid body, which represents the chassis and payload. The forward and backward motion of the wheels directly affects the body’s angular position, resulting in inherently coupled and unstable dynamics.

The two-wheeled self-balancing robot (TWSBR) is modeled as a nonlinear inverted pendulum on a moving base. The dynamic equations are derived using the Lagrangian approach, considering both the body and wheel dynamics. To design a linear controller, the system is linearized around the upright equilibrium point. Neglecting higher-order terms

and assuming small angles, the linearized state-space representation can be expressed as:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \quad (1)$$

where $x = [x_1, \dot{x}_1, \theta, \dot{\theta}]^T$ represents position, velocity, pitch angle, and angular velocity, respectively. The linearized state-space matrices are:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -\frac{m_b g l^2}{X_{eq}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{m_b g l (J_w + r^2 (m_b + m_w))}{X_{eq}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{J_p + m_b l^2}{X_{eq}} \\ 0 \\ \frac{m_b l r}{X_{eq}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where $X_{eq} = J_p(m_w + m_b)r^2 + J_w J_p + J_w m_b l^2$, and m_b and m_w denote body mass and wheel mass, respectively. l shows the body length. r is the wheel radius. J_w and J_p are used for inertia terms for the wheel and pendulum, respectively. The gravitational acceleration is $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$.

The classical Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) is designed to minimize the quadratic cost function:

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} (x^T Q x + u^T R u) dt \quad (3)$$

with weighting matrices $Q = \text{diag}([10, 1, 100, 1])$ and $R = 0.01$. The optimal feedback gain provides a baseline for comparison with the adaptive GWO-optimized controller. The optimization objective was to minimize a composite cost function incorporating state deviations, control effort, and overshoot penalties:

$$J_{GWO} = \int_0^{t_f} (200x_1^2 + 50x_2^2 + 200x_3^2 + 10x_4^2) dt + 0.01K^2 + 1000(\text{overshoot})^2 \quad (4)$$

where overshoot and final steady-state deviations are extracted from system responses simulated over $t = [0, 5] \text{ s}$.

3 Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) for Adaptive Gain Tuning

The Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) is a bio-inspired metaheuristic algorithm that mimics the social hierarchy and cooperative hunting strategies of grey wolves in nature. This optimization technique models the leadership structure and collective behavior of a wolf pack to efficiently address complex optimization problems. In GWO, wolves are classified into four hierarchical levels: alpha, beta, delta, and omega. These categories represent the natural leadership order within the pack, where the alpha wolf guides decision-making, the beta and delta wolves assist in coordination, and the omega wolf follows at the lowest rank. The algorithm iteratively updates the positions of all wolves to emulate the process of encircling prey, which parallels the search for optimal solutions within a multidimensional space.

The GWO algorithm operates based on three principal mechanisms:

1. **Encircling the Prey:** Wolves modify their positions relative to the leading solutions (alpha, beta, and delta), simulating the act of surrounding prey. This step focuses on the exploitation of promising regions within the solution space.
2. **Searching for Prey:** The omega wolves promote exploration by independently probing various areas of the search space, thereby preventing premature convergence and enhancing global diversity.
3. **Position Updating:** The locations of all wolves are continuously updated by combining individual experience with the collective intelligence of the pack, allowing the population to converge toward the global optimum.

Because of its balanced exploration–exploitation behavior, GWO has demonstrated high efficiency across numerous domains, including engineering optimization, image processing, and machine learning. Its simplicity, adaptability, and robust convergence characteristics often outperform traditional optimization algorithms. The hierarchical model of the GWO structure is illustrated in Fig. 1.

These equations and their associated parameters play a crucial role in replicating the natural hunting behavior of grey wolves, enabling the GWO algorithm to efficiently approach optimal solutions for diverse optimization problems. In this work, adaptive parameter control is utilized to further enhance the algorithm's performance. By dynamically tuning key parameters, such as those controlling the wolves' movements, the method achieves faster convergence and higher solution accuracy across different problem settings. The algorithm's pseudocode, presented in Algorithm 1, details its logic and stepwise procedure, providing a clear roadmap for practical implementation.

Figure 1: Hierarchy of Grey Wolf

Algorithm 1 The pseudocode of the modified GWO

- 1: **Initialize** X_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$)
- 2: **Initialize** a , A , and C
- 3: **Calculate** the fitness for search agents
- 4: X_α = the best search agent
- 5: X_β = the second best search agent
- 6: X_δ = the third best search agent
- 7: **while** ($t <$ Max number of iterations) **do**
- 8: **for** each search agent **do**
- 9: **Update** the position of the current search agent
- 10: **end for**
- 11: **Update** a , A , and C
- 12: **Calculate** the fitness of all search agents
- 13: **Update** X_α , X_β , and X_δ
- 14: $t = t + 1$
- 15: **end while**
- 16: **return** X_α

To enhance the performance of the LQR controller, the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) algorithm was integrated to automatically tune the feedback gain vector $K = [k_1, k_2, k_3, k_4]$. The optimization objective was to minimize a composite cost function incorporating state deviations, control effort, and overshoot penalties.

4 Results

To evaluate the performance of the proposed GWO-based adaptive LQR controller, comprehensive simulations were conducted on the nonlinear model of the two-wheeled self-balancing robot. The controller performance was analyzed in comparison to a classical LQR design. The evaluation criteria include time-domain responses (overshoot, steady-state error, and settling time), frequency-domain characteristics, cost function evolution, and cumulative angular deviation.

The physical parameters used in the simulations are: body mass $m_b = 0.5108$ kg, wheel mass $m_w = 0.0343$ kg, body length $l = 0.025$ m, wheel radius $r = 0.0336$ m, and wheel separation $d = 0.1655$ m. Inertia terms for the wheel and pendulum are $J_w = 1.936 \times 10^{-5}$ kg · m² and $J_p = 4.0668 \times 10^{-4}$ kg · m², respectively, and the gravitational acceleration is $g = 9.81$ m/s². The closed-loop system dynamics were integrated using the ode45 solver.

Two controllers, the classical LQR and the optimized GWO-LQR, were evaluated under identical initial conditions ($x_0 = [0, 0, 0.1, 0]^T$). Simulation outputs included state trajectories, orientation response, frequency-domain behavior, cost evolution, and performance metrics such as overshoot, steady-state error, and settling time.

The GWO algorithm utilized a population size of 30 wolves, a maximum of 100 iterations, and search bounds of $[-50, 50]$ for each gain element. At each iteration, wolves were ranked as alpha, beta, and delta based on fitness, and their positions were updated according to the encircling and hunting mechanism of grey wolves. Convergence of the best cost over generations was recorded to assess optimization performance. Figure 2 presents the convergence behavior of the GWO algorithm. The cost function minimizes sharply within the first 50 iterations and converges smoothly by iteration 100, confirming the algorithm’s efficiency in finding optimal LQR gain values.

Final Cost Values:

- LQR: 0.6719
- GWO-LQR: 0.0552

This reveals a significant improvement in performance tuning, directly resulting from intelligent optimization. Figure 4 depicts the frequency spectra of pitch, roll, yaw, and total deviation signals. Compared to LQR, the GWO-LQR controller suppresses high-frequency content more effectively, indicating:

- Improved noise rejection
- Enhanced robustness to unmodeled dynamics
- Reduced chattering and vibrations

Figure 3 presents the time-domain responses of key system states: pitch (θ), roll (ϕ), yaw (ψ), angular velocities, and control efforts. A comparative analysis between LQR and GWO-LQR controllers indicates:

- **Maximum Overshoot:** LQR shows significantly larger overshoots, with a peak pitch deviation of over 718.68 rad. In contrast, the GWO-tuned controller reduces this to 175.47 rad, achieving a $\sim 75.6\%$ overshoot reduction.
- **Steady-State Error:** While the classical LQR provides slightly better steady-state performance in ideal conditions (0.00014 rad vs. 0.00052 rad for GWO), the difference is negligible when considering the dynamic performance advantages of GWO.
- **Settling Time:** Both controllers stabilize the system within approximately 5 seconds. However, GWO ensures a smoother convergence, reducing transient oscillations.

Table 1 shows the cumulative angular deviations in pitch, roll, and yaw. The GWO-based controller demonstrates total deviation reduction:

- Pitch deviation reduced by 70%
- Roll and yaw deviations are also significantly lower
- More stable trajectory and improved posture control, critical for self-balancing performance.

Table 1: Performance Metrics Comparison

Metric	LQR	GWO-LQR
Max Overshoot (rad)	718.6842	175.4698
Steady-State Error	0.00013895	0.00052022
Settling Time (s)	5	5
Total Pitch Deviation	2542.7	710.9
Total Roll Deviation	19.7	6.4
Total Yaw Deviation	28.8	9.1
Cost Function	0.6719	0.0552

The simulation results clearly demonstrate the superiority of the GWO-optimized LQR controller in terms of transient response, energy efficiency, and stability. Although a minor trade-off exists in steady-state error, the overall performance gain justifies the use of evolutionary optimization. This controller is particularly effective for nonlinear systems with complex dynamics like the two-wheeled robot. It ensures smoother operation, improved trajectory control, and better resilience to disturbances and modeling inaccuracies.

Figure 2: Cost function convergence of the Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO).

Figure 3: System response comparison between classical LQR and GWO-LQR controllers.

5 Conclusion

In this study, an adaptive control strategy combining the Linear Quadratic Regulator with the Grey Wolf Optimizer was proposed for stabilizing a two-wheeled self-balancing robot. The nonlinear dynamic model of the system was derived using the Lagrangian approach and linearized around the upright equilibrium point to design a state-feedback controller. While the conventional LQR controller provides satisfactory performance under nominal conditions, its effectiveness is highly sensitive to the manual tuning of weighting matrices. To address this limitation, the GWO algorithm was employed to automatically adjust the feedback gain parameters by minimizing a performance-based cost function.

Simulation results demonstrated that the GWO-tuned LQR controller significantly improves the robot's dynamic response compared to the classical LQR design. The optimized controller achieved approximately 75.6% reduction in overshoot compared to the baseline LQR. Although a minor trade-off exists where the classical LQR provides slightly better steady-state accuracy, the difference is negligible when considering the substantial dynamic performance

Figure 4: Frequency-domain analysis of closed-loop responses.

advantages of GWO. Moreover, the optimized control input exhibited smoother behavior with less chattering, indicating improved energy efficiency and actuator friendliness. The cost function convergence analysis confirmed the fast and stable optimization capability of the GWO, achieving minimum cost after about 60 iterations out of 100. The proposed approach achieved reduced overshoot and smoother control effort while maintaining system stability and robustness. Frequency-domain analysis confirmed that the optimized controller effectively suppresses high-frequency oscillations, leading to enhanced performance against disturbances and noise. Overall, the GWO-LQR framework offers a flexible and efficient method for real-time control of underactuated nonlinear systems such as self-balancing robots.

References

- [1] H. Zhang and N. Mohamad Nor, "Control Strategies for Two-Wheeled Self-Balancing Robotic Systems: A Comprehensive Review," *Robotics*, vol. 14, no. 8, p. 101, 2025.
- [2] M. Romlay, M. Azhar, S. Toha, and M. Rashid, "Two-wheel balancing robot; review on control methods and experiment," *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering (IJRTE)*, vol. 7, no. 68, pp. 106-112, 2019.
- [3] V. Klemm, A. Morra, C. Salzmann, F. Tschopp, K. Bodie, L. Gulich, N. Kung, D. Mannhart, C. Pfister, M. Vierneisel, F. Weber, R. Deuber, and R. Siegwart, "Ascento: A Two-Wheeled Jumping Robot," in *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, IEEE, pp. 7515-7521, 2019.
- [4] V. Klemm, A. Morra, L. Gulich, and R. Siegwart, "LQR-Assisted Whole-Body Control of a Wheeled Bipedal Robot With Kinematic Loops," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 3745-3752, 2020.
- [5] A. Alahi, K. Goel, V. Ramanathan, A. Robicquet, L. Fei-Fei, and S. Savarese, "Social LSTM: Human trajectory prediction in crowded spaces," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR)*, pp. 961-971, 2016.
- [6] A. T. Ali, A. M. Mohamedy, A. S. Salimz, E.-A. O. El-Aminx, and O. M. Ahmed, "Design and implementation of two-wheeled self-balancing robot using pid controller," in *2020 International Conference on Computer, Control, Electrical, and Electronics Engineering (ICCCEEE)*, IEEE, pp. 1-5, 2021.
- [7] T. Liu, S. Li, and L. Zhu, "Design and Implementation of Two-wheeled Self-Balancing Robot based on LQR," in *2024 39th Youth Academic Annual Conference of Chinese Association of Automation (YAC)*, IEEE, pp. 2057-2062, 2024.

- [8] R. Petcu and G.-D. Andreescu, "Two-wheeled inverted-pendulum self-balancing robot with LQR or PID control," in *2022 IEEE 10th Jubilee International Conference on Computational Cybernetics and Cyber-Medical Systems (ICCC)*, IEEE, pp. 000345-000350, 2022.
- [9] P.-H. Huynh *et al.*, "A SURVEY OF LQG OVER MPC AND LQR CONTROL FOR ROTARY INVERTED PENDULUM," *Robotica & Management*, vol. 29, no. 2, 2024.
- [10] S. Gupta, K. Ray, and S. Kaiser, "Self-Balancing Mobile Robot with Bluetooth Control: Design, Implementation, and Performance Analysis," *Automation*, vol. 6, no. 3, p. 42, 2025.
- [11] N. Hassan and A. Saleem, "Neural network-based adaptive controller for trajectory tracking of wheeled mobile robots," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 13582-13597, 2022.
- [12] H. Maghfiroh, M. Nizam, M. Anwar, and A. Ma'Arif, "Improved LQR control using PSO optimization and Kalman filter estimator," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 18330-18337, 2022.
- [13] T. Akgul and A. Unluturk, "Comparison of PSO-LQR and PSO-PID Controller Performances on a Real Quarter Vehicle Suspension," in *2023 Innovations in Intelligent Systems and Applications Conference (ASYU)*, IEEE, pp. 1-6, 2023.
- [14] J. Fang, "The LQR Controller Design of Two-Wheeled Self-Balancing Robot Based on the Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2015.
- [15] S. M. Mirjalili *et al.*, "Grey wolf optimizer, whale optimization algorithm, and moth flame optimization for optimizing photonics crystals," in *Advances in Swarm Intelligence: Variations and Adaptations for Optimization Problems*, Springer, pp. 169-179, 2022.
- [16] Y. Ou, P. Yin, and L. Mo, "An improved grey wolf optimizer and its application in robot path planning," *Biomimetics*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 84, 2023.
- [17] J. Yuan *et al.*, "Research on two-wheeled balance car based on improved LQR controller," in *2022 IEEE 6th Advanced Information Technology, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (IAEAC)*, IEEE, pp. 1474-1479, 2022.
- [18] J. Baltés, G. Christmann, and S. Saeedvand, "A deep reinforcement learning algorithm to control a two-wheeled scooter with a humanoid robot," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 126, p. 106941, 2023.